

Heavy Metal Contamination in Urban Soils: Health Impacts on Humans and Plants: A Review

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Abstract:

This research looks at how the growth of cities and industries affects the levels of heavy metals in the soil, which can impact people's health. We find out where the pollution comes from, such as factories, car fumes, and improper waste disposal, by reviewing existing studies. We use different methods to test the soil for heavy metals and study how exposure to these metals in urban areas affects people's health. The evidence shows a connection between high levels of heavy metals in city soil and health problems like breathing issues, brain disorders, and overall toxicity in the body. We also

explore how these metals get into the human body, highlighting the importance of understanding how they are available and the ways people are exposed. To deal with polluted city soils, we look at different ways to manage the soil and suggest sustainable methods to reduce heavy metal pollution. Our discoveries add to what we know about urban environmental health, emphasizing the need for actions to protect city residents. Ultimately, this study aims to give important information and insights to policymakers, city planners, and public health officials for managing and lessening the health risks linked to heavy metal contamination in urban soils.

Keywords: *Heavy metal, urban soils, health impacts, human, plant, policy, monitoring.*

Introduction

The Heavy metals, known for their weight and density, are a concern for the environment and health due to their toxicity and lasting presence. Though there's no strict weight-based definition, "heavy metals" usually refers to elements with

specific characteristics, having a high density from a significant number of protons, neutrons, and electrons (Wang, et al., 2024).

These metals, even in small amounts, can disrupt biological processes, negatively impacting both human health and the environment. For

example, lead (Pb), historically used in paint and gasoline, poses severe risks to neurological and developmental health, especially in children. Mercury (Hg) tends to build up in aquatic organisms, and methylmercury, a form of mercury, poses health risks through eating contaminated fish. Cadmium (Cd), often found in industrial processes, accumulates in soils and crops, posing a risk to human health through food consumption. Arsenic (As), whether naturally occurring or from industry, contaminates water sources, causing significant health concerns (Zhang, et al., 2024).

These metals can occur naturally or result from human activities like industry, mining, and agriculture. They build up in soils, affecting plant growth and contaminating food crops (Niazi, et al., 2023). Runoff from industrial sites and improper waste disposal can contaminate water bodies, risking aquatic ecosystems and human health. Some metals become airborne through industrial emissions, contributing to air pollution (Su, et al., 2024). Governments and environmental agencies regulate metal levels in air, water, soil, and food to protect public health and the environment. Monitoring programs assess concentrations to identify risks and guide mitigation strategies (Eid, et al., 2024).

Urban environments, impacted by industry and human activity, often contain metals like lead, cadmium, mercury, arsenic, chromium, nickel, copper, and zinc (Monib, 2023). Regulations, pollution control technologies, and sustainable urban planning aim to reduce metal release, safeguarding public health (Mansoet al., 2024). Key features of heavy metals include high density, toxicity at low levels, persistence, bioaccumulation, non-biodegradability, and varying solubility in water. Sources include natural processes and human activities like industry. Common examples include lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, and nickel. Due to potential risks, heavy metal presence is closely monitored and regulated

(Jagaba, et al., 2024). Heavy metals can harm the body by building up in cells and tissues, damaging important molecules like proteins and DNA. This accumulation, known as bioaccumulation, occurs through various processes and can lead to negative effects. Research shows that heavy metals, especially when binding to DNA and nuclear proteins, contribute to the oxidative damage of biological molecules.

Heavy metals, like lead, mercury, cadmium, and copper, can enter the human body through drinking contaminated water or consuming crops grown on polluted land, these metals are toxic and contribute to environmental hazards, leading to oxidative stress in cells and various health issues, including brain damage, cancer, and developmental abnormalities, dumpsites, frequented by scavengers, pose a risk as materials from these sites can end up as food for animals, creating vectors for pests and diseases, plants absorbing high concentrations of heavy metals from contaminated soil pose health risks, especially when consumed, as these metals accumulate in tissues, the water around dumpsites becomes contaminated, causing heavy metal poisoning through irrigation and domestic use, (see table 1), this contamination can lead to allergies, skin infections, and act as a breeding ground for disease vectors, posing serious health threats to the surrounding area (Aithani, & Kushawaha, 2024).

The consequences of heavy metal toxicity include potential mental disorders, harm to blood components, and damage to vital organs like the lungs, liver, and kidneys (Parui, et al., 2024). This review highlights the sources and processes that expose and accumulate heavy metals in the human body. Additionally, it explores the metabolism and mechanisms behind heavy metal toxicity, and discusses the signs and symptoms of their harmful effects on the human body.

Table 1. Some Heavy Metals Harm Humans, Plants, and the Environment

Metal	Sources of Contamination	Routes of Exposure	Health Impacts	Challenges on Humans	Challenges on Plants and Environment
Lead (Pb)	High levels near industrial areas, traffic sources	Ingestion of contaminated food and water, inhalation of airborne particles	Neurological issues, developmental delays	Limited awareness among urban residents, Inadequate monitoring, Soil testing and remediation	Soil degradation, Disruption of ecosystems, Water contamination, Loss of biodiversity, Impact on soil microorganisms
Cadmium (Cd)	Elevated in areas with industrial activities	Consumption of contaminated plants and animals, inhalation of contaminated dust	Kidney damage, cardiovascular issues	Lack of effective remediation methods, Persistence of cadmium in soil	Soil and water contamination, Impact on plant growth, Disruption of nutrient cycling, Health risks to aquatic life
Mercury (Hg)	Found in soil near certain industries and coal-fired power plants	Bioaccumulation in the food chain, consumption of contaminated fish and seafood	Neurological damage, respiratory problems	Difficulties in regulating industrial emissions, Bioaccumulation in the food chain	Conversion to toxic methylmercury, Impact on aquatic ecosystems, Long-term ecosystem disruption
Chromium (Cr)	High concentrations in areas with metal processing and tannery activities	Ingestion of contaminated food, inhalation of airborne particles	Respiratory issues, skin irritation	Inadequate waste disposal practices, Limited awareness among local communities	Groundwater contamination, Soil and water contamination, Impact on plant health
Arsenic (As)	Elevated levels in mining areas and near industrial sources	Ingestion of contaminated water, food, and plants, inhalation of airborne particles	Skin and lung cancers, cardiovascular issues	Lack of affordable and effective treatment options for affected individuals	Long-term soil contamination, Impact on aquatic ecosystems, Health risks to terrestrial and aquatic organisms
Nickel (Ni)	Found in areas with metal processing and fossil fuel combustion	Consumption of contaminated food, inhalation of airborne particles	Respiratory problems, skin allergies	Limited research on health impacts, Inadequate regulations on industrial emissions	Soil and water contamination, Impact on plant growth, Disruption of nutrient cycling, Health risks to aquatic life

Sources of Heavy Metal Contamination

Heavy metal contamination in the environment can come from both natural and human-related sources. Understanding these sources is crucial for effective environmental management and developing strategies to reduce contamination. Rocks and minerals naturally release heavy

metals into the soil and water through weathering processes (Mitran, et al., 2024). Volcanic eruptions can also contribute to heavy metal contamination by releasing substantial amounts into the atmosphere. Various industries, including mining, metal smelting, and manufacturing, release heavy metals into the environment as byproducts of their processes. For example, mining operations expose metals

from the Earth's crust (Du, et al., 2024). Poor disposal of industrial waste, electronic waste, and household waste can introduce heavy metals into soil and water, turning landfills into potential contamination sources if not managed properly (Chakraborty, et al., 2024).

The use of certain fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, and livestock manure can also contribute to heavy metal concentrations in the soil, in urban areas, stormwater runoff can carry heavy metals from roads, buildings, and surfaces into water bodies, contributing to contamination (Niazi, et al., 2023). Industrial activities, vehicle exhaust, and other sources release heavy metals into the air, and these metals settle on land or water through atmospheric deposition (Singhal, et al., 2024). Burning fossil fuels, like coal and oil, releases heavy metals such as mercury into the air, eventually depositing into soil and water bodies. The extraction of minerals from the Earth's crust exposes and releases heavy metals, with runoff from mining sites carrying metals into nearby water bodies (Paruet al., 2024).

The process of extracting metals from ores, particularly through smelting, can release metals and metal compounds into the air, potentially causing contamination in the vicinity of smelting facilities. Industries discharging wastewater with heavy metals directly into water bodies contribute to contamination (Karimi Darvanjooghi, et al., 2024). Effluents from sewage treatment plants, containing heavy metals from domestic and industrial sources, also contribute to water contamination. Previous industrial practices, like leaded gasoline and lead-based paints, have left a legacy of contamination in urban areas, and even if these practices are stopped, residual contamination may persist (Liang, et al., 2024).

Transport and Fate of Heavy Metals in Urban Soils

The movement and impact of heavy metals in urban soils are complex processes influenced by factors like land use, human activities, soil properties, and environmental conditions. Understanding how heavy metals travel in urban

environments is crucial for effective management and mitigation. These metals can be transported through soil erosion caused by factors like rainfall, construction, or improper land management, with the eroded soil and attached heavy metals carried by runoff and deposited in other areas (Liu, et al., 2024). Additionally, particulate matter containing heavy metals settles on urban soils from the atmosphere, with emissions from industrial processes, traffic, and human activities contributing to this deposition. Water movement through the soil profile can transport dissolved heavy metals, potentially affecting groundwater and nearby surface water bodies.

Soil properties, such as texture and organic matter, influence how heavy metals move, with clayey soils retaining metals more effectively than sandy soils (Belcik, et al., 2024). Different land uses in urban areas, such as industrial, residential, and commercial zones, can impact the types and amounts of heavy metals present. Industrial areas often have higher concentrations due to manufacturing processes (Ou, et al., 2024). Plants contribute to heavy metal transport by absorbing metals from the soil, affecting the cycling of metals between soil and vegetation (Azizi, et al., 2023). Human activities like construction, traffic, and the use of products such as pesticides and fertilizers can disturb soil, potentially releasing heavy metals (Montes-Rocha, et al., 2024). Heavy metals can attach to soil particles through processes like sorption and adsorption, influenced by soil properties. They can also form complexes with organic matter and other soil constituents, affecting their solubility and mobility (Luo, et al., 2024). The use of plants to extract, accumulate, and stabilize heavy metals in the soil is called phytoremediation, where specific plant species are chosen for their ability to absorb and store metals in their tissues.

In cases of severe contamination, remediation techniques like soil washing, chemical immobilization, or excavation and disposal may be used to reduce heavy metal concentrations in urban soils (Tennakoon, et al., 2024). Changes in the chemical forms of heavy metals, known as speciation, can impact their bioavailability and

toxicity. Transformation processes, including oxidation-reduction reactions and the conversion of one metal form to another, play a role. Heavy metals may accumulate in specific soil components, such as organic matter or iron oxides, influencing their distribution and potential for long-term retention (Kumar, et al., 2024). Implementing soil conservation practices like cover crops, contour plowing, and erosion control measures can help minimize the transport of heavy metals through erosion and runoff (Ji, et al., 2024).

Characteristics of Urban Soil

Urban soil science, a relatively young field since the mid-1970s, focuses on soil in urban environments, heavily impacted by human activities like mixing materials, importing/exporting, and contamination. Urban soil is characterized by disturbances like compaction, sealing, and removal of natural substrates. It's found in parks, roadsides, sports fields, rivers, landfill sites, and mining areas due to urbanization (Tang, et al., 2024).

While urbanization offers advantages like better healthcare, it transforms natural ecosystems into human-dominated systems, affecting soil properties. Urbanization, through activities like vehicle emissions, waste disposal, and building, poses risks to ecosystems and human health, a shift from natural to urban soil brings structural changes, impacting soil functions like production, pollution control, and hydrological cycling (Haarstrick, & Sharma, 2024).

Soil scientists play a crucial role in understanding urban soil for both human well-being and urban ecosystem health, as the physical, chemical, and biological properties of urban soil differ significantly from natural soil. Urbanization alters landscapes, leading to soil sealing and reducing soil functions. Investigating urban soil is essential for addressing threats to urban soil functions and ensuring the health of urban ecosystems and human well-being (Chukwuemeka, et al., 2024).

Urban Soil Pollution Impacts

Heavy metal contamination, known for its significant health and environmental risks, poses threats to ecosystems and human well-being. Exposure to lead, especially in children, can lead to cognitive and developmental impairments (He, et al., 2024). Mercury exposure, particularly in fetuses and young children, results in neurological and developmental issues. Arsenic and cadmium, classified as carcinogens, elevate the risk of cancer with prolonged exposure. Inhaling airborne heavy metal particles, like lead and cadmium, contributes to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Ali, et al., 2024). Chronic exposure to heavy metals, such as cadmium and lead, harms kidneys and the liver, causing long-term health issues. Lead and mercury can affect reproductive health and fetal development, leading to birth defects and fertility issues. Consuming food or water contaminated with heavy metals causes gastrointestinal problems and damages the digestive system (Huang, et al., 2024).

Heavy metals bio-accumulate, posing risks to higher-level consumers as they move up the food chain, they disrupt ecosystems, impacting plant and animal species abundance and diversity, leading to imbalances in ecological communities, leaching of heavy metals from soils contaminates groundwater, risking drinking water sources and human health (Selvasembian, et al., 2024). Anthropogenic activities, like industrial emissions, contribute to airborne heavy metal particles, causing air pollution with health impacts and deposition onto soils and water bodies (Neisi, et al., 2024). Heavy metals persist long-term in the environment, resulting in chronic exposure and ecological impacts (Di Duca, et al., 2024).

Governments implement regulations and standards to limit heavy metal release and concentrations in air, water, soil, and food (Jagaba, et al., 2024). Remediation strategies, including phytoremediation, soil washing, and chemical immobilization, reduce heavy metal concentrations in contaminated sites. Sustainable practices in industries, agriculture, and urban development minimize heavy metal

release and promote environmentally friendly alternatives (Dingley, et al., 2024). Informing the public about heavy metal risks and promoting proper waste disposal and pollution prevention reduce exposure (Niazi, et al., 2023). Regular monitoring of environmental media and human exposure assesses mitigation effectiveness and identifies emerging risks. Addressing heavy metal contamination impacts requires a comprehensive, coordinated approach involving regulatory frameworks, scientific research, public awareness, and sustainable practices (Yang, et al., 2024).

Heavy metals, like lead, mercury, cadmium, and copper, can get into the human body through polluted drinking water, soil, or crops, these toxic metals create environmental dangers and oxidative stress, contributing to various health problems, including cancer, exposure to heavy metals can result in brain damage, mental health issues, lung cancer, and harm to unborn fetuses (Huang, et al., 2024).

Some metals directly harm DNA, causing chromosomal breaks. The dumpsite, where scavengers gather materials, becomes a contamination source, affecting animals that may spread diseases to nearby homes (Monib, et al., 2023). Plants absorbing high metal concentrations from soil pose health risks through the food chain, especially when consumed by humans, if the body fails to process and eliminate these metals, they can accumulate in soft tissues, causing toxicity, chronic ingestion of toxic metals has long-term harmful effects, becoming noticeable only after several years of exposure (Taufiq, et al., 2024).

Water sources around the dumpsite become contaminated through leaching and rainwater, posing risks to crops and domestic use, using this water may result in heavy metal poisoning, allergies, and skin infections, the dumpsite also becomes a breeding ground for disease vectors, causing serious health problems in the area (Zahra, et al., 2024).

Pollutants, organic and inorganic, in urban soil:

Research in environmental science has focused on organic pollutants in urban soil due to their complex structure and harmful effects on the environment and human health. Persistent organic pollutants (POPs), including polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins, polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDD/Fs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) such as dichloro-diphenyl-trichloroethane (DDT), hexachlorohexanes (HCHs), and hexachlorobenzene (HCB), have gained significant attention (Muñoz-Arnanz, et al., 2024).

In addition to organic pollutants, heavy metals are a concern in urban soil, heavy metals like lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), mercury (Hg), and arsenic (As), as well as essential elements like copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), cobalt (Co), manganese (Mn), and nickel (Ni), become pollutants in high concentrations (Ozturk, H., et al., 2023). Urban soil serves as a significant sink for heavy metals, discharged from various anthropogenic sources such as traffic emissions, industrial activities, waste disposal, construction materials, power plants, and mining operations (Zhu, et al., 2024).

Cadmium (Cd)

A rare metal in Group II-B of the periodic table, has seen increased production in recent years, commonly used in semiconductors, nickel-cadmium batteries, electroplating, PVC, various alloys, pigments, and control rods for nuclear reactors, cadmium contamination in soil and water arises from mining and smelting industries, atmospheric pollution, sewage sludge application, and fossil fuel burning (Guo, et al., 2024).

Diseases caused by cadmium exposure exhibit symptoms such as bone pain, pathological fractures, and signs of kidney impairment, cadmium toxicity affects organs such as the liver, placenta, kidneys, lungs, brain, and bones, research on humans and animals reveals

significant effects like osteoporosis, disruptions in calcium metabolism, renal stone formation, and hypercalciuria due to cadmium exposure. Symptoms may include nausea, vomiting, abdominal cramps, dyspnea, and muscular weakness, with severe exposure potentially leading to pulmonary edema and death, long-term exposure may cause morphopathological changes in the kidneys (Anjum, et al., 2024).

Cadmium and its compounds are highly water-soluble, facilitating bioaccumulation. Smokers, exposed to cadmium through tobacco, are more susceptible to intoxication than non-smokers, the presence of cadmium in smokers is due to tobacco plants' ability to accumulate it from the soil, non-smokers are exposed through food and other pathways, but at lower levels (Zuhra, et al., 2024). Cd is associated with a disease called Itai-Itai, meaning "it hurts" in Japanese. Clinical conditions like anosmia, cardiac failure, cancers, cerebrovascular infarction, emphysema, osteoporosis, proteinuria, and cataract formation in the eyes have been linked to cadmium. Cadmium interacts with essential nutrients, causing toxicity effects. Animal studies show that 50% of inhaled cadmium gets absorbed in the lungs. High cadmium exposure during human pregnancy can lead to premature birth and reduced birth weights (Bhardwaj, et al., 2024).

Arsenic (As)

Arsenic (As) is a highly toxic metalloid found in group V-A of the periodic table, it is used in various applications such as insecticides, pyrotechnics, and metal hardening, arsenic is present naturally and due to human activities like agriculture and industry, leading to environmental pollution (Li, et al., 2024).

Inorganic arsenic, like arsenite and arsenate, poses severe health risks, causing cancers in the lungs, liver, bladder, and skin. Global concerns arise from arsenic-contaminated drinking water, where levels exceeding WHO guidelines are harmful, contamination can result from the disposal of arsenical chemicals or natural deposits, arsenic toxicity can be acute or chronic, with chronic exposure known as arsenicosis, often affecting the skin (Ganie, et al., 2024).

Despite its toxicity, certain forms of arsenic have been adapted for medical use in treating diseases like syphilis and cancer (Li, et al., 2024).

Chromium (Cr)

Chromium (Cr) is a versatile metal with dual effects on humans and animals depending on its oxidation state and concentration, it originates from various industries, with Cr (III) and Cr (VI) being the most significant forms. Cr (III) is essential for living organisms and is used in industries like electroplating, paint manufacturing, and textiles. However, industries often release both Cr (III) and highly toxic Cr (VI) into the environment, causing contamination (Spears, et al., 2024). Hexavalent chromium (Cr (VI)) is acutely toxic, mutagenic, and carcinogenic. It is soluble and mobile in various environments. Cr (III), at lower concentrations, is beneficial in human and animal diets, aiding in glucose and lipid metabolism, however, at high concentrations, Cr (III) can interfere with metabolic processes. Cr (VI) is known to cause cancer, allergic dermatitis, and nasopharyngeal cancer (Jasu, et al., 2024).

Exposure to chromium compounds, especially through inhalation or contact with the skin, can lead to severe health issues, including ulcer formation and slow healing, high exposure inhibits the capacity to reduce methemoglobin to hemoglobin, numerous experiments indicate that chromate compounds can cause DNA damage, leading to chromosomal aberrations and other genetic alterations (ME, et al., 2024).

Lead (Pb)

Lead is a harmful pollutant found in soil, water, and air, originating from sources like petroleum, electronic industries, batteries, paint, stained glass, and biocide preparation, leaded gasoline in cars contributes significantly to lead pollution globally, with over a thousand tons produced annually from road traffic. Soils, plants, and food absorb these emissions, posing a potential threat to health (Aziz, et al., 2024).

Lead is highly toxic, affecting humans, animals, plants, and microbes. It can cause developmental disorders in fetuses, infants, and young children, leading to brain damage, respiratory issues,

central nervous system intoxication, and male infertility, lead specifically targets memory and learning processes in the brain through inhibiting N-methyl-d-aspartate receptors (NMDAR), blocking neurotransmission, inhibiting neuronal voltage-gated calcium channels (VGCCs), and reducing the expression of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (Bjørklund, et al., 2024).

Mercury

Mercury is known as the most toxic heavy metal in the environment, causing poisoning known as acrodynia or pink disease, it is released by industries like pharmaceuticals, paper, agriculture, and chlorine production, continuous exposure to metallic, organic, and inorganic mercury can harm the brain, kidneys, and developing fetus (Bukhari, et al., 2024).

Mercury is present in most foods and beverages, especially in marine foods, organic mercury, found in fatty fish and lean fish liver, is easily absorbed by bio membranes. Micro-organisms convert mercury in soil and water into methyl mercury, a toxin that accumulates with fish age and trophic levels, both mercuric chloride and methyl mercury are declared highly carcinogenic by the EPA (Onyeaka, et al., 2024).

The nervous system is sensitive to all types of mercury, and increased exposure can lead to altered brain functions, shyness, tremors, memory problems, irritability, and changes in vision or hearing. Metallic mercury vapors, when inhaled at higher levels, can cause lung damage, vomiting, diarrhea, nausea, skin rashes, increased heart rate, or blood pressure. Organic mercury poisoning symptoms include depression, memory problems, tremors, fatigue, headache, and hair loss, making diagnosis challenging (Dong, & Li, 2024). Due to health risks, the standard for drinking water has been set at lower levels by the Environmental Protection Act and World Health Organization.

Heavy Metals Disrupt Plant Growth, Affecting Uptake, Nutrients, Metabolism, and Genetics

Heavy metals, such as lead, cadmium, mercury, and copper, exert diverse and far-reaching impacts on plant growth and development, these metals disrupt essential physiological, biochemical, and molecular processes within plants, notably affecting photosynthesis by interfering with chlorophyll production and light-harvesting complexes (Nagajyoti, et al., 2010). Additionally, heavy metals impede water and nutrient uptake, leading to imbalances in essential elements and disturbances in mineral absorption, root systems experience alterations in morphology, growth, and branching, influencing overall root development (Jagota, et al., 2024).

Genetic and physiological changes occur, including DNA damage and mutations, resulting in stunted growth, reduced biomass, and compromised reproductive processes, reactive oxygen species (ROS) production under heavy metal stress leads to oxidative damage, with long-term ecological consequences disrupting biodiversity in plant communities (Singh, et al., 2024). Further, heavy metals can translocate to edible plant parts, posing risks for human health when contaminated produce is consumed, plant ecosystems have developed adaptation and tolerance mechanisms, including detoxification pathways (Thiruvengadam, et al., 2024). Effective remediation strategies, such as phytoremediation and soil amendments, play a crucial role in mitigating adverse effects, interplay between heavy metals and plant growth is vital for devising comprehensive strategies to safeguard plant ecosystems and the broader environment (Etesami, & Glick, 2024).

The mechanisms governing the uptake of heavy metals by plants involve complex processes occurring at the root-soil interface and extending into cellular and physiological pathways (Wang, et al., 2024), root uptake involves both passive and active processes, with heavy metal ions moving along concentration gradients or using energy-dependent transport systems (Chakraborty, 2024). Once inside root cells,

metal ions may undergo complexation with various ligands, facilitating their transport into the plant's vascular system (Qin, et al., 2024), translocation from roots to aerial plant parts occurs through the xylem, influenced by factors like metal speciation and plant species (Shri, et al., 2024).

Some plants exhibit hyperaccumulation, accumulating high metal concentrations as a defense mechanism, mycorrhizal associations can enhance nutrient absorption but also increase the risk of heavy metal uptake, these mechanisms is crucial for managing and mitigating the impacts of heavy metal uptake by plants, ensuring environmental and human health in metal-contaminated soils (Wahdan, et al., 2024).

The impacts of heavy metals on plant nutrient dynamics are crucial environmental and agricultural concerns, heavy metals disrupt the normal uptake and utilization of essential nutrients, competing with elements like iron, zinc, and manganese for uptake by plant roots, this competition leads to imbalances in nutrient availability, affecting vital processes like photosynthesis and enzyme activities, the presence of heavy metals alters the biochemical composition of plants, impacting the nutritional quality of crops, this disruption not only affects individual plants but poses risks for the entire food chain, as contaminated crops may lead to reduced nutrient content and compromised nutritional value when consumed by animals or humans. Mitigating these impacts requires comprehensive strategies, including soil remediation techniques, sustainable agriculture, and the development of metal-tolerant plant varieties (Patani, et al., 2024).

The disruption of microbial activity resulting from heavy metal contamination in soil has cascading effects on nutrient cycling and soil fertility, significantly impacting plant health and ecosystem dynamics, soil microbes play a crucial role in decomposing organic matter, cycling nutrients, and maintaining soil fertility, heavy metals inhibit microbial activity, slowing down the release of nutrients into the soil and compromising the availability of elements like

nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur for plant uptake, disruption of microbial communities affects symbiotic relationships, such as mycorrhizal associations, diminishing the soil's ability to support plant growth and maintain a healthy nutrient balance, strategies for soil remediation and promoting microbial resilience play a vital role in mitigating the adverse impacts of heavy metal pollution on nutrient cycling and plant well-being (Lloret, et al., 2024).

The effects of heavy metals on plant metabolism involve disruptions in biochemical and physiological processes, impacting overall plant health, heavy metals interfere with photosynthesis by disrupting chlorophyll synthesis and light-harvesting complexes, compromising the plant's ability to convert sunlight into energy, these metals also disturb enzymatic activities involved in metabolic pathways, affecting respiration, nutrient assimilation, and the synthesis of secondary metabolites, the disruption of plant metabolism under heavy metal stress often leads to altered carbohydrate and protein metabolism, impacting the overall nutritional composition of the plant (Ilyas, et al., 2024).

Oxidative stress, characterized by the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), contributes to cellular damage, plants exposed to heavy metals may exhibit reduced growth, biomass, and overall vigor, these effects is essential for developing effective strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of heavy metal contamination and ensure the resilience and sustainable growth of plant ecosystems (Khalil, et al., 2024).

The effects of heavy metals on plants extend to induce significant genetic and physiological changes that impact growth, development, and overall well-being (Chau, et al., 2024), heavy metal exposure can result in DNA damage and mutations (Liu, et al., 2024), interfering with normal cellular processes and leading to changes in gene expression patterns, physiologically, heavy metals influence plant function, including photosynthesis, respiration, and nutrient uptake, disruption of photosynthesis occurs through interference with chlorophyll synthesis and light-

harvesting complexes, impacting energy production, heavy metals also disturb enzymatic activities involved in essential metabolic pathways. Physiological changes manifest as observable symptoms, such as stunted growth, reduced biomass, and altered reproductive processes, oxidative stress and genetic mutations contribute to an overall decline in plant health, these responses is crucial for developing strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of contamination, protect biodiversity, and ensure the sustainability of plant ecosystems in environments affected by heavy metal pollutants (Salam, et al., 2024).

Monitoring and Assessment, Regulatory Framework, and Standards

Monitoring heavy metals is crucial for environmental management, regulatory compliance, and risk assessment, involving processes like sampling and analysis of soil, water, and air using techniques such as atomic absorption spectrometry and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (Mallick, et al., 2024). Biological monitoring assesses bioaccumulation in various organisms, providing insights into ecosystem impacts and health risks. Remote sensing helps identify at-risk areas and assess land cover changes, while data analysis uses statistical methods to identify patterns and variations. Regulatory compliance includes setting standards, monitoring industries, and enforcing measures, with public awareness efforts engaging communities (Sundhar, et al., 2024).

Long-term monitoring programs establish baseline levels, compare data over time, and use adaptive management. International collaboration ensures data sharing and standard harmonization for effective monitoring. Regulatory frameworks and standards for heavy metals vary globally, with organizations like the WHO, UNEP, EU, EPA, and MEE providing guidelines and directives.

India's CPCB sets standards under pollution control acts, incorporating risk assessments and monitoring programs. Reporting requirements,

enforcement mechanisms, and adaptability to scientific knowledge changes are integral to regulatory approaches. Collaboration between countries and organizations ensures consistent practices, emphasizing the importance of effective regulation and monitoring for preventing and mitigating the environmental and health impacts of heavy metal contamination (Feng, et al., 2024).

Remediation and Mitigation Strategies

Remediation and mitigation strategies for heavy metals aim to reduce or eliminate these contaminants in the environment, minimizing their impact on ecosystems and human health (Wan, et al., 2024). Common strategies include using hyper-accumulator plants that absorb and accumulate heavy metals, cultivating them in contaminated areas, and then removing the plants to prevent re-contamination. Microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi, transform or immobilize heavy metals in the soil, and amendments like lime or organic materials change their chemical forms, reducing mobility and bioavailability (Niazi, et al., 2023, Cui, et al., 2024). Washing soil with chemical solutions removes heavy metals, and recovered metals can be returned to the site. Constructed wetlands with vegetation filter and absorb heavy metals from water, and electric fields induce metal movement for collection and removal. Impermeable barriers, liners, or caps isolate contaminated soils, preventing metal migration (Sridhar, & Parimalarenganayaki, 2024).

Reforestation on mining sites stabilizes soil, reducing erosion and heavy metal runoff. Land use policies and industrial emission regulations contribute to contamination control. Raising awareness and promoting environmentally conscious practices among communities is crucial, along with education and training on waste management and pollution prevention (Wei, et al., 2024). Ongoing monitoring assesses remediation effectiveness, and integrated approaches involving collaboration among scientists, engineers, regulators, and

communities are key to successful remediation projects.

Case Studies

Worldwide case studies highlight the environmental and health challenges associated with heavy metal contamination (Noor, et al., 2024). The 1984 Union Carbide pesticide plant disaster in Bhopal released toxic chemicals, including heavy metals, causing immediate casualties and ongoing soil and groundwater contamination, resulting in persistent health issues for local residents (Haber, 2024). Flint's 2014 water crisis exposed the population to elevated lead levels from aging pipes, leading to a public health emergency with neurological and developmental effects, particularly affecting children, emphasizing the importance of water quality management (Burns, 2024). Artisanal gold mining in Ailaoshan released mercury, contaminating soil and water and impacting fish, affecting communities dependent on fish consumption and highlighting challenges in managing pollution from small-scale mining (Tang, et al., 2017).

In Toyama Prefecture, Japan, mining activities caused cadmium pollution in the Jinzu River, leading to severe health effects, while Cerro de Pasco, a mining town, faced extensive environmental contamination, posing challenges related to relocation and impacting the local population (Martínez-Alier, 2023). The Matanza-Riachuelo River Basin in Argentina, one of the most polluted areas, experienced heavy metal contamination from industrial discharges, affecting aquatic ecosystems and local communities (Thakur, et al., 2024). These cases highlight the need for effective environmental management, regulatory oversight, and community engagement to prevent and address heavy metal contamination. They also stress the importance of sustainable practices in industries and the necessity for monitoring and remediation efforts to safeguard human health and the environment.

Future Trends and Research Needs

Continuous and evolving, ongoing research on heavy metals aims to address emerging challenges and enhance our understanding of their behavior, impacts, and mitigation strategies (Yang, et al., 2024). Future trends and research priorities involve investigating the environmental fate, transport, and toxicity of engineered nanoparticles containing heavy metals. There is also a focus on understanding the behavior and risks associated with novel metal compounds and emerging contaminants. Crucially, research examines the influence of climate change on the mobility, bioavailability, and environmental fate of heavy metals, including the impact of extreme weather events on their release and transport. Additionally, studies explore the health effects of cumulative exposure to multiple heavy metals and other pollutants, considering the role of genetic factors in individual susceptibility to heavy metal toxicity (Kou, et al., 2024).

Advances include the development and optimization of sustainable remediation technologies like bioremediation, nano-remediation, and electro-kinetic methods, with an emphasis on evaluating the effectiveness of combining different remediation strategies for complex contamination scenarios. The use of advanced techniques, including omics technologies, for biomonitoring and assessing ecosystem health exposed to heavy metals is essential. Research identifies and validates new bio-indicator species for monitoring heavy metal contamination and investigates interactions between micro-plastics and heavy metals in urban environments. In the context of urban agriculture, assessing risks and benefits in areas with potential heavy metal contamination is critical (Sharma, & Sharma, 2024).

Integrating heavy metal regulations with broader environmental policies, working toward global harmonization of standards, and using data analytics and machine learning for large datasets are crucial aspects. Predictive models for assessing the long-term fate and transport of heavy metals under changing environmental

conditions are being developed (Xue, et al., 2024).

Implementing community-based interventions to reduce exposure, especially in vulnerable populations, enhancing public awareness and education, exploring sustainable methods for recycling and recovering metals from waste streams, and integrating circular economy principles are part of the research agenda. Encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration, applying a "One Health" approach, establishing global monitoring networks, promoting open data platforms, and focusing on sustainable practices are key drivers in addressing future research needs in the field of heavy metals. This holistic approach ensures a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges posed by heavy metals and supports the development of effective management and mitigation strategies (Jota Baptista, et al., 2024).

Community Awareness and Involvement

Ensuring community awareness and engagement in addressing heavy metal contamination challenges is vital for informed decision-making and promoting environmental and public health, this involves organizing educational workshops, integrating environmental education into school curricula, and holding community meetings to discuss local concerns, disseminating information through various channels, including publications, websites, and social media, provides real-time updates to the community, training programs on environmental health and skill-building workshops empower community members to monitor and address local environmental issues (Cutts, et al., 2024).

Encouraging participation in citizen science initiatives for monitoring heavy metal levels and promoting safe gardening practices are effective local initiatives. Supporting community advocacy groups, capacity building for leaders, and implementing health screenings contribute to community empowerment (Abass, et al., 2024). Culturally sensitive communication

strategies and collaboration with local leaders enhance effective messaging and build trust. Emergency response plans, evacuation drills, and partnerships between community members, authorities, NGOs, and industry stakeholders collectively address heavy metal issues, feedback mechanisms, surveys, and focus group discussions help understand community perceptions and concerns (Arora, et al., 2024).

Developing long-term sustainability programs and involving youth in awareness campaigns ensure continuous community engagement. Ongoing efforts and genuine collaboration are essential for building and sustaining community awareness and involvement in environmental protection and public health initiatives related to heavy metals (Zhou, et al., 2024).

Policy Recommendations and Interdisciplinary Approaches

Addressing heavy metal contamination requires a comprehensive approach encompassing regulatory frameworks, monitoring systems, public awareness, and sustainable practices (Ding, 2024), recommendations include regularly updating environmental quality standards, implementing emission limits for industries, and integrating heavy metal considerations into land use planning. Comprehensive monitoring networks, early warning systems, and open data platforms enhance surveillance and information sharing. Public awareness programs, community involvement, and promotion of alternative materials are crucial for prevention.

Investing in research, innovative remediation technologies, and international cooperation fosters effective cleanup. Interdisciplinary collaboration involving environmental science, toxicology, public health, engineering, and social sciences is vital, this includes understanding metal transport, identifying sources, optimizing remediation, and assessing health risks through combined toxicological and epidemiological studies (Nega, et al., 2024). Engineers work on sustainable practices, biologists on bioaccumulation, and social sciences on

community-based research, policy expert's focus on compliance monitoring, data science integrates information, and economic collaboration includes cost-benefit analysis. Interdisciplinary training, remote sensing, innovative monitoring, and international partnerships contribute to holistic heavy metal management, ensuring sustainable strategies and successful implementation (Silakari, et al., 2024).

Discussion

Discussing heavy metals involves exploring various aspects, including their sources like industry, mining, agriculture, and urban runoff, and the pathways they take into the environment through air, water, and soil. Considering the environmental consequences on ecosystems, biodiversity, and human health, especially for vulnerable groups, is crucial. Emphasizing interdisciplinary collaboration, sharing success stories, and assessing regulatory frameworks are key. Discussing community roles, innovative technologies, regional variations, economic impacts, education, and emerging trends contributes to a comprehensive understanding. Exploring industry responsibility, adaptive management, and ethical dimensions adds depth to the conversation. Engaging in such discussions promotes dialogue, diverse perspectives, and collaborative solutions for managing heavy metals.

Conclusion

In conclusion, heavy metals pose significant challenges to the environment and public health, requiring a collaborative and interdisciplinary approach for effective management. Lead, cadmium, mercury, and arsenic, found in industrial processes, agriculture, and everyday products, are widespread in air, water, soil, and food, collaboration across environmental science, toxicology, engineering, public health, social sciences, and policy is essential. Researchers, policymakers, industry professionals, and communities must work together to address the complexities of heavy metal contamination, key concerns include

environmental impacts on ecosystems, soil degradation, water pollution, and disruption of biodiversity, chronic exposure poses severe health risks, particularly for vulnerable populations. Interdisciplinary collaboration is crucial, involving environmental scientists, engineers, health professionals, social scientists, and policymakers for holistic solutions.

Stringent regulatory frameworks are vital for controlling emissions, setting standards, and preventing heavy metal release, with regular updates based on the latest scientific knowledge, innovative and sustainable remediation technologies, such as phytoremediation and bioremediation, show promise. Community engagement is key, empowering communities for localized issues and fostering a sense of ownership.

Global cooperation and information-sharing are essential for addressing the transboundary nature of environmental pollution, collaborative efforts between countries, international organizations, and research institutions can lead to standardized approaches and sharing best practices. Technological advancements, including data science, remote sensing, and sensor technologies, enhance monitoring, modeling, and early detection, these tools contribute to informed decision-making and adaptive management, moving forward, a commitment to sustainable practices, continuous research and innovation, and the integration of diverse perspectives will be pivotal, by comprehensively and collaboratively addressing this multifaceted challenge, society can work towards minimizing the environmental and health impacts of heavy metals and fostering a more sustainable and resilient future.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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